

Forecasting Moonlighting in Latvia using ARIMA Model

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Abstract

This study is aimed to find a suitable Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model to forecast moonlighting in Latvia. Using quarterly data for the period of 2002 Q1 to 2015 Q4 obtained from Eurostat, this study suggests that the appropriate ARIMA model for moonlighting in Latvia is ARIMA (0,1,1). The fitted ARIMA (0,1,1) model is used to forecast moonlighting in Latvia for next ten quarters. No significant difference between forecasts and actual data has been found.

Keywords: *Moonlighting, ARIMA Model, Forecasting, Latvia*

I. INTRODUCTION

Simultaneous employment in multiple jobs is known as moonlighting or second job holding (Shisko and Rostker (1976), Krishnan (1990), Allen (1998), Conway and Kimmel (1998), Böheim and Taylor (2004), Renna and Oaxaca (2006), Adhikary and Pal (2012), Yamb and Bikoue (2016)). Diverse reasons are responsible for moonlighting. The rationed supply of working hours into primary job at the utility maximizing level may compel a worker to spend idle working hours into secondary job/jobs. This is known as hours constraint motive of moonlighting (Shisko and Rostker (1976), O'Connell (1979), Krishnan (1990), Allen (1998), Conway and Kimmel (1998), Böheim and Taylor (2004), Adhikary and Pal (2012)). In addition to the hours constraint, the interest for work in heterogeneous jobs may also act as a crucial motivation behind moonlighting (Conway and Kimmell (1998), Kimmel and Conway (2001)). Liquidity constraint, the inability to maintain a standard of living like the rest of society due to low income, is another significant basis for moonlighting (Abdukadir (1992)). Negative financial shock (Boheim and Taylor (2004), hedging strategies against job uncertainty (Bell, Hart and Wright (1997)), overtime pay regulations (Friesen (2001)), portfolio diversification between steady but low-paying job and well paid but less stable jobs (Paxson and Sicherman (1996)) etc. are also important factors of moonlighting.

Incidence of moonlighting is growing due to flexible working conditions (Baines and Newell (2004), Combos, McKay and Wright (2007)). Skills may be acquired through moonlighting (Dickey, Watson and Zangelidis

(2009), Panos, Pouliakas and Zangelidis (2011)) but moonlighting may strengthen shadow economy due to tax evasion from secondary employments (Frey and Schneider (2000), Schneider (2010), Barth and Ognedal (2005)). Markets with both public and private provisions may also suffer from distortions in terms of performance and productivity due to moonlighting (Biglaiser and Ma (2007)). Forecasting the potential of moonlighting is necessary to evaluate the effects of moonlighting on the national economy. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), introduced by Box and Jenkins (1976), is a powerful method of forecasting with low forecast errors. This forecasting method just requires historical time series data for the variable being forecasted. This paper is aimed to find a suitable ARIMA model to forecast moonlighting in Latvia using historical quarterly data from Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lfs/data/database>) for the period of 2002 Q1 to 2015 Q4.

Latvia is a developed nation in the Baltic region of Northern Europe. After gaining independence from Soviet Union, the nation established itself as one of the advanced economies in Europe by privatizing most of the productive resources and emphasizing on export led growth. Latvia had the fastest-growing economy in Europe up to the middle of 2008. After years of tremendous economic growth, the country had experienced one of the world's steepest downturns in 2008-09 as a result of the credit bubble. The Latvian economy was hardest hit by the global financial crisis in 2009. In the fourth quarter of 2009, the country experienced signs of recovery and began to recover thereafter. The service sector makes up a substantial portion of the Latvian economy. Data from Eurostat reveal that many employees in Latvia concurrently hold several jobs (moonlight).

II. METHODOLOGY

An ARIMA(p, d, q) model is the combination of Auto Regressive (AR) process of order p , a Moving Average (MA) process of order q and d , the order of integration (I) to make the series stationary. The AR process is the long-term memory model where the past (or lagged) values of the variable have additive effects on the current value of the variable. A time series $\{Y_t\}$ follows AR(p) process if:

$$Y_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t$$

where $\phi_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ are the coefficients and the error term ε_t is a white noise process.

If the time series variable is expressed in terms of past errors as explanatory variables, then it is called MA process.

The MA(q) process of the time series $\{Y_t\}$ is:

$$Y_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$$

where μ is the mean of the process and $\theta_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, q$ are the coefficients.

The ARMA(p, q) process of the time series $\{Y_t\}$ is the combination of AR(p) and MA(q) process:

$$Y_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$$

If the time series is non-stationary and d times differencing is required to make it stationary, then it is called ARIMA(p, d, q) process and can generally be expressed as:

$$\Delta^d Y_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 \Delta^d Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 \Delta^d Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p \Delta^d Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$$

The success of ARIMA modeling (the Box-Jenkins methodology) lies in its forecasting performance. The ARIMA modeling involves four steps. The first step requires identification of the values of p , d and q using autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation function (PACF). The next step is the estimation of the chosen ARIMA(p, d, q) model. The third step involves diagnostic checking (or testing whether the residuals of estimated model are white noise). The final step is the forecasting using estimated ARIMA(p, d, q) model. This study is designed to estimate a suitable ARIMA(p, d, q) model using quarterly data for the period of 2002 Q1 to 2015 Q4 to forecast moonlighting in Latvia.

III. RESULTS

The quarterly data of Latvia from the first quarter of 2002 to the last quarter of 2015 on “number of employed persons (NEP)” and “number of employed persons having second job (SJH)”, are downloaded from Eurostat. Then moonlighting rate $MOON_t$ is calculated in terms of percentage of SJH_t to NEP_t at time t , ($MOON_t = \frac{SJH_t}{NEP_t} \times 100$). The time series plot of $MOON_t$ is presented in Figure – 1.

The ACF and PACF of $MOON_t$ is presented in Figure -2. From this figure it is clear that there is unit root in $MOON_t$ since ACF did not fall as quickly as lag increases and it needs to be differenced to make it stationary. For robustness, we perform unit root tests for both level and first differences, which are presented in Table – 1. Both the Augmented Dicky Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron (PP) tests confirm that the quarterly data on moonlighting for the period of 2002 Q1 to 2015 Q4 are non-stationary in level but stationary in the first difference of MOON (d_MOON). Figure -3 presents correlogram of ACF and PACF of the d_MOON. Since ACF of d_MOON falls after lag one, d_MOON is stationary. Therefore, $d = 1$. Since, both the ACF and PACF of d_MOON falls quickly after lag 1, $p = 1$ and $q = 1$. Therefore, the expected ARIMA model is ARIMA(1,1,1).

The estimates of ARIMA(1,1,1) model is presented in Table – 2. This table clears that the coefficient of MA(1) is significant while the coefficient of AR(1) is not significant. This model requires to be compared with other possible models using different model selection criteria (Akaike Information Criterion, Schwarz Criterion and Hannan-Quinn Criterion). The ideal model is one that meets these criteria’s minimum values. The comparison results are presented in Table – 3. The smallest values of various selection criteria rests on ARIMA(0,1,1). Therefore, the best model to forecast moonlighting in Latvia is ARIMA(0,1,1).

Next step involves diagnostic tests of the identified best model ARIMA(0,1,1). This necessitates confirmation of normality and the stationarity of the residuals of ARIMA(0,1,1) model. The normality tests of residuals are presented in Table – 4. Since p value of all the test statistic is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis that residuals follow normal distribution is accepted. Figure – 4 represents the ACF and PACF plots of the residuals of ARIMA(0,1,1) which confirms that the residuals are stationary. The stationarity of residuals is also confirmed in Table -5. Therefore the model ARIMA(0,1,1) is appropriate for forecasting.

Figure – 1: Time series plot of Moonlighting in Latvia

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Figure – 2: ACF and PACF of MOON

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table 1: Unit Root Test of MOON

	Intercept		Trend and Intercept	
	Level	First Difference	Level	First Difference
ADF Test Statistic (Based on SIC, Max Lag=10)	-2.473501	-10.19526*	-3.161692	-10.24589*
Phillips Perron Test Statistic	-2.174290	-11.75163*	-3.047220	-15.34726*

Note: * denote rejection of the null hypothesis at 1% level of significance.

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Figure -3: ACF and PACF of first difference of MOON (d_MOON)

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table – 2: Parameter estimates of ARIMA(1,1,1) model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.027036	0.039000	-0.693237	0.4913
AR(1)	0.172719	0.250669	0.689033	0.4939
MA(1)	-0.632944	0.239193	-2.646169	0.0108
F-statistic	3.395126	Prob(F-statistic)	0.024697	

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table – 3: Evaluation of various ARIMA models

Model	Akaike Info Criterion	Schwarz Criterion	Hannan-Quinn Criterion
ARIMA(0,1,1)	1.935757	2.045248	1.978098
ARIMA(1,1,0)	1.982440	2.091931	2.024781
ARIMA(1,1,1)	1.966143	2.112131	2.022598

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Figure – 4: ACF and PACF of residuals of ARIMA(0,1,1)

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table – 4: Tests for normality of Residuals

	Test Statistic	P value
Doornik-Hansen test	0.228787	0.891907
Shapiro-Wilk W	0.991755	0.969264
Jarque-Bera test	0.557242	0.756827

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table -5: Unit Root Test of residuals of ARIMA(0,1,1)

	Intercept		Trend and Intercept	
	Level	P value	Level	P value
ADF Test Statistic (Based on SIC, Max Lag=10)	-6.681402	0.0000	-6.802151	0.0000
Phillips Perron Test Statistic	-6.635868	0.0000	-6.760093	0.0000

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

Table - 6: Forecast of Moonlighting in Latvia using ARIMA(0,1,1)

Year	MOON Actual	MOON Predicted	95% Confidence interval	
			Lower	Upper
2016 Q1	5.99	5.68	4.50071	6.85905
2016 Q2	5.67	5.66	4.33356	6.97954
2016 Q3	5.50	5.63	4.18057	7.08586
2016 Q4	5.67	5.61	4.03825	7.18152
2017 Q1	4.54	5.59	3.90432	7.26879
2017 Q2	4.49	5.56	3.77723	7.34922
2017 Q3	4.06	5.54	3.65584	7.42394
2017 Q4		5.52	3.53931	7.49381
2018 Q1		5.49	3.42697	7.55948
2018 Q2		5.47	3.31832	7.62146

Source: Own computation based on secondary data from Eurostat

In order to compare predicted and actual data, the quarterly data for the period of 2016 Q1 to 2017 Q3 is preserved. Table – 6 presents actual and forecasted data on moonlighting in Latvia with their 95% confidence interval. No significant difference between forecasts and actual data has been found. Therefore ARIMA(0,1,1) is the best model to predict moonlighting in Latvia.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aims to identify an appropriate Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model of moonlighting in Latvia. Using quarterly data for the period of 2002 Q1 to 2015 Q4 obtained from Eurostat, this study suggests that ARIMA (0,1,1) is the suitable ARIMA model for moonlighting in Latvia. The fitted ARIMA (0,1,1) model is used to forecast moonlighting in Latvia for subsequent ten quarters. Forecasts and actual data have not been shown to differ significantly. Moreover, moonlighting in Latvia will decline over time according to the forecast.

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